

ITEMS ON SOME TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING TERMS

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Lexis is one of the most important elements to be considered when discussing English language teaching as the many intricacies and subtleties forming up vocabulary can constitute an important barrier in front of effective and correct acquisition. It has often been pointed out that a major obstacle to comprehending texts in their disciplines for technical students of English is technical vocabulary as it would be expected (highly specialized words usually used only by specialists and which are as a rule taken care of by the subject teachers), or general vocabulary which is usually acquired by the time students reach college, but a third intermediate lexical proportion of scientific and technological texts and known as *sub-technical, semi-technical or nontechnical vocabulary*. This consists of items of vocabulary from normal English operating within a science context. The aim of this dissertation is to investigate teaching technical words in English the extent to which this vocabulary is semantically and stylistical distinct from the same vocabulary but in a general English context, and then to outline the translation difficulties that Romanian business students technicians and engineers and also computer programmers with these the terms; in other words we shall try to establish the degree of semantic overlap that exists between English and Uzbek as regards this vocabulary.[1.193]

A very detailed theoretical presentation of what sub-technical vocabulary is, as seen through the various conclusions of those that have studied it along time is given by scientists. Besides the differences existing in the labeling of this special range of words existing between the fully technical and the general English, some researchers preferring the term *sub technical* others using *nontechnical* and still others using *semi-technical*, the problem is further complicated by the existence of different definitions.

We investigate the degree of lexical and conceptual overlap between the sub-technical vocabulary of technology in English, the focus of our research being the creation of reading and lexical materials as follows:

- to train university students to read English prose for specific purposes. The sub-technical vocabulary he refers to is formed;
- mainly of Latinate words that form part of the vocabulary of general educated usage;
- referring to linguists whom we acknowledge as the first to use the term sub-technical;
- Sub-technical vocabulary as “context-independent words which occur with high frequency across disciplines”. This definition applies to those words that have the same meaning in several scientific or technical disciplines. Then they go on to say: “To these words we have added those “common” words that occur with special meanings in specific scientific and technical fields. Together, the two sets of words make up the English sub-technical vocabulary.”

The extent to which this overlap or rather the lack of it can facilitate or, on the contrary, adversely affect comprehension and act as a barrier to acquisition of knowledge. The study comprises an empirical investigation of the problems which students of technology are likely to encounter in reading technological texts and it should be conducted using a de-contextualised word-level exercise, students should be asked to translate a set of words from English into Uzbek or Russian and then to make up sentences using these words. The list of sub-technical lexical items used for the test was partly drawn from frequency list of positive key words and partly made up based on our own intuition and teaching experience; this latter part includes words such as motor vehicle, accreditation, automatic section, abrasive, damage repairs, range, aloud, base, barrel, combat, condemn, that are felt to have a high frequency of occurrence in the published technical English materials students will encounter in their English classes. However, both the lexical items of key words and those added by us from various teaching materials have been distinguished from technical lexis based on an essentially intuitive method rather than on any empirical data, this approach being motivated on the one hand by the absence of any available large corpus from which statistical conclusions could be drawn, and, on the other, by the fact that, as it has been pointed out before in this study, when speaking about technical/sub-technical vocabulary we seem to be dealing with rather fluid tendencies rather than hard-and-fast categories. Thus, although a number of additional words were at first included in the list (equity, return, lending, margin, draft, spread, turnover) they were later excluded as it was felt that they required a precise technical explanation by the subject teacher, so they belonged more properly under the heading of "technical vocabulary".[2.103-116].

Even if the central meaning does not coincide in the two languages, it is important to make students aware of the fact that a familiar word may have an unfamiliar meaning, so that the trap of preconception regarding a lexical item can be avoided.

The following principles should be taken into consideration:

1. Background of the learners.
2. Aims of the course
3. Text-types
4. Level of knowledge
5. Organization of the class
6. Sequence of the texts
7. Exercise for each unit
8. Teaching approaches.
9. Teaching aid.

Articles on science and technology published in English books, magazines and newspapers can be used as teaching materials, for these un-simplified (authentic) articles are different from those of the test-oriented textbooks. Technical articles have no plots, which would bore the students. Besides, this is a selective course, and the students are from different majors, such as Automotive Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Material Engineering. When selecting the materials, try to choose the subject-related, practical ones which would arouse the interest of the students and meet their needs, and avoid using long, dull and highly specialized texts. It may be more appropriate to look for text that are more interesting in order to generate the motivation needed to learn English. Therefore, some articles on *automobile development, electric vehicle, engine*

construction, robot, numerical control system, transistor circuit and radio communication are selected respectively from Financial Times. International Business, Motor Vehicle Technology, ARRL Amateur a washer, dital AV amplifler and projector were also selected. With the factors considered, these selected materials could attract the students attention. Some of the materials are too long and would make teaching dull. Therefore, they were cut into proper length to meet the needs. Translation exercises should be arranged in the end of each text

In fast, all the majors are interwoven or overlapped in some fields and there are twilight zones. With the factors considered, these selected materials could attract the students attention.

Student – centered discussions can be held once in a while in class- the students are divided into groups of 4-5 people and assigned appropriate passages to translate, so that they have opportunities to practice using dictionaries and deciding word meanings. After the discussions, one student from each group read the translation in class, and in the end the teacher would comment on the translation and correct the errors. Discussions make every student use his brain, and the problems that the students have can be quickly diagnosed, the class going on in a relaxing atmosphere. The students might be good at their subject, but not that good at English. Grammar-Translation Method can be party used. Grammar is used as an aid to study. The structure of difficult sentences is explained, and long, difficult sentences are translated into the target language, especially long sentences and sentences with attributive clauses. With the teaching going on, some basic translation techniques, such as amplification, repetition, conversion and division are integrated into the text translation gradually.

It the teaching process the existing pictures are made use of fully. For example, in the teaching of the text about the engine, the illustrations of the engine and components can be used; in the teaching of the text about transistor circuit, some of the mentioned electronic components are shown to the students, making the teaching easier.

At the end of the per term students are tested. The open-book test can be used, i.e. they should be allowed to use dictionaries in the test. The test is an achievement one, consisting of two parts:

1. Explain the terms (or words) in English:
2. Translate passages into Uzbek.

Thus we can check the students' ability to use simple English words or sentences to explain technical terms or words they have learnt. For example: microphone- a device for transforming sound waves into an electric current.

Another check student's knowledge is of two short passages, one taken from the materials the students have learnt and the other from the materials they have not read before, so that both ability and achievement are tested. The students write answers by themselves, no four possible answers as in the case of "multiple choice". The results of the tests show that the students can pick much knowledge through learning the materials and do the translation.[4.304]

From this study we can see that students can learn both English and knowledge from English for specific purpose course. English for technical purpose is not a matter of teaching "specialized varieties" of English. The fact that language is used for a specific purpose does not imply that it is a special form of language, different in kind from other forms. General English

is the basis of Technical English. If the General English is poor, the students can not go further in English for technical purpose. Both of them are closely related, and there is no special grammar structure for English for technical purpose. Some scientists point out that even the differences in vocabulary are far less significant than might be expected.

There are 4 types of vocabulary:

- a) structural: e.g. are, this, however
- b) general: e.g. table, run, dog, road, cause;
- c) sub-technical: engine, spring, valve, aced;
- d) technical: auricle, schist some, fissure;

It is only the last category that will show any significant variation. It is found that in an extensive corpus of scientific and technical writing, technical vocabulary accounted paragraphs taken from the course material:

This grinding operation is completed by a single spindle grinding head which operates in conjunction with a positioning table on which the component is placed by the robot. Features of this station include an automatic wheel-dressing unit and a visual display which indicates the end of effective wheel life. Wheel feed is actuated by a hydraulic system giving variable feed rate and thrust.(63 words)

On completion of the grinding cycle, the head is transferred by the robot to the CERA washing module, which consists of four separate stations- two for washing and two for drying. This washing module is, in effect, a modified version of a CERA free standing washing machine, with inter-station parts handling. Within the unit is a CERA 135 filter, a 10 bar(145 lbf/ in 2) pressure wash pump, and blow-off and exhaust fans. (73 words)

There is no special sentence structure in the two paragraphs. Most of the words are general. Sub-technical words, such as “grind”, “spindle”, “actuate” account for only a small percentage. There are only two technical words (“hydraulic” and “robot”), and they usually have one meaning and can easily be solved through their subject knowledge. For the students it is the polysemic words that make the decision of the word meaning difficult.[5.147-159].

There are some limitations in this research. Because of the difficulty to get the more detailed video materials and pictures for the teaching materials, sometimes only the black and white illustrations in the texts were used. With the visual aids such as the video tapes, photos, etc., the teaching could be much easier, and students could have been further motivated. In further teaching, some extra items such as not-so-difficult “ Uzbek-English translation” and “speaking” could be added to technical English teaching. As for “speaking” , the teacher can ask some questions on the learned text for the students to answer. For example, after finishing a text on the car safety feature, the teacher can ask questions like, “Can you name one or two safety features of a car?”, “What is the function of anti-submarine ramp?”, “What is ABS?”, etc. The teacher guides the students to speak. Gradually, the students can be required to use simple English to talk on their subjects.

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In the present article some methods of teaching English technical terms to the higher school students and some techniques of translation of technical terms are viewed.

Technical term, typology, frequency, approach, process, reliability.

